

IPPT_TWINN - Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity
in polymer processing technologies
of the Faculty of Polymer Technology

**WP1 – ADVANCED HYBRID PROCESSING
TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE DEMANDS
D1.4 EVALUATED BONDING
STRENGTH BETWEEN COMPONENTS
PRODUCED BY HYBRID TECHNOLOGY**

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Executive summary

Task 1.4 of Work Package 1 (WP1) of IPPT_TWINN project focused on assessing the use of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) in hybrid polymer processing technologies, specifically in the context of combining injection moulding (IM) and fused filament fabrication (FFF). The goal was to determine whether CAN-modified PP and ABS materials could provide improved bonding strength in overmoulded or overprinted hybrid structures. Materials were prepared via reactive extrusion, upscaled and used for filament production, and distributed among partners for overprinting of prepared substrates (PP-based injection moulded plates).

A multi-partner Round Robin test was conducted to evaluate the dimensional accuracy, mechanical properties, and print quality of standard PP and ABS filaments across various FFF printers. ABS demonstrated good dimensional stability and reproducibility across partners, while PP showed more inconsistencies attributable to shrinkage and process sensitivity. Printer-specific behaviour remained the dominant influence on mechanical outcomes.

CAN-modified formulations were successfully processed; however, their performance did not meet initial expectations. Although material characterization confirmed the presence of dynamic covalent networks, these structural modifications did not consistently translate into improved mechanical behaviour or enhanced interfacial bonding. Peel tests of overprinted samples showed limited peel strength improvements, even when annealing was employed.

Despite this outcome, Task 1.4 provides valuable insight into the current limitations of CAN materials in hybrid processes. The results highlight the need for further optimization of vitrimer chemistry, and processing conditions. The findings contribute to a better understanding of what is required for CANs to support hybrid manufacturing strategies and meet future performance demands effectively. Furthermore, broadened research on individual technologies and materials was conducted within the framework of the project, resulting in multiple published scientific papers¹⁻⁴.

Introduction

Hybrid manufacturing technologies that combine conventional polymer processing routes with additive manufacturing offer substantial opportunities for improved material efficiency, design freedom, and component performance. Within this context, Task 1.4 of WP1 addresses the integration of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) into hybrid processes involving injection moulding (IM), and fused filament fabrication (FFF). CAN materials possess dynamic covalent bonds that allow reprocessability, welding, and enhanced interfacial adhesion—features that make them promising candidates for multi-material and overmoulded structures.

One component of Task 1.4 involved a coordinated Round Robin study to assess how standard PP and ABS filaments behave across different printers and institutions. This provided an essential baseline for evaluating dimensional accuracy, mechanical repeatability, and process sensitivity—factors that significantly influence hybrid manufacturing outcomes.

To investigate this potential, CAN-modified PP and ABS formulations were developed through reactive extrusion and subsequently upscaled into granulates in quantities used for injection moulding of testing specimens, and substrates for overprinting, as well as used for filament production. The same material batches were shared among all beneficiaries for overprinting using their equipment.

The second component focused on overprinting experiments, where CAN-based composite filaments were printed onto injection-moulded grafted PP and vitrimer PP plates. Peel strength measurements were used to evaluate whether CAN chemistry would promote stronger bonding through dynamic covalent exchange reactions, and how these results compared to baseline bonding behaviour previously measured in Task 1.1.

However, as demonstrated in this deliverable, the CAN formulations tested did not provide the anticipated improvements in mechanical or interfacial performance, nor did annealing. While dynamic networks were successfully introduced into the materials, their practical influence on hybrid bonding strength remained limited under the processing conditions applied. These findings highlight the complexity of translating vitrimer chemistry into reliable manufacturing benefits and indicate the need for further formulation and process optimization.

Methods used

Round-Robin test

The Round-Robin study aimed to evaluate 3D printed specimens produced on various 3D printing devices and to assess the mechanical characteristics and precision of 3D printers.

In Table 1 are listed materials and printers that were used for 3D printing. The commercially available filaments utilized were:

- **Polypropylene (PP) natural** from Fiberlogy and
- **DURAPRO Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS)** from Extrudr were used.

The 3D printers involved in the study included:

- Tumaker BIGFOOT PRO 500 DUAL (FTPO),
- Creality Ender 3 (FTPO),
- Prusa MK4 (IWK and AITIIP),
- Prusa XL (IWK), Qidi X Max (PCCL),
- Bambulab X1C (BME),
- Method X (BME), and
- INTAMSYS HT (AITIIP).

Table 1: Sample list

Sample number	Sample description
822_2025_0034_PP-Tumaker	Parallel and perpendicular print from FTPO
822_2025_0034_PP-Ender	Parallel and perpendicular print from FTPO
822_2025_0034_PP-MK4	Parallel and perpendicular print from IWK
822_2025_0034_PP-PrusaXL	Parallel and perpendicular print from IWK
822_2025_0034_PP-QIDI	Parallel and perpendicular print from PCCL
822_2025_0034_PP-X1C	Parallel and perpendicular print from PCCL
822_2025_0034_PP-MethodX	Parallel and perpendicular print from BME
822_2025_0034_PP-X1C V2	Parallel and perpendicular print from BME
822_2025_0034_PP-HT	Parallel and perpendicular print from AITIIP
822_2025_0034_PP-MK4 V2	Parallel and perpendicular print from AITIIP
822_2025_0034_ABS-Tumaker	Parallel and perpendicular print from FTPO
822_2025_0034_ABS-Ender	Parallel and perpendicular print from FTPO
822_2025_0034_ABS-QIDI	Parallel and perpendicular print from IWK
822_2025_0034_ABS-PrusaXL	Parallel and perpendicular print from IWK
822_2025_0034_ABS-MK4	Parallel and perpendicular print from PCCL

Sample number	Sample description
822_2025_0034_ABS-X1C	Parallel and perpendicular print from PCCL
822_2025_0034_ABS-MethodX	Parallel and perpendicular print from BME
822_2025_0034_ABS-X1C V2	Parallel and perpendicular print from BME
822_2025_0034_ABS-HT	Parallel and perpendicular print from AITIIP
822_2025_0034_ABS-MK4 V2	Parallel and perpendicular print from AITIIP

For Round-Robin tests, two models were chosen. For the determination of dimensional accuracy and flexural properties standard ISO 178 flexural specimen in two orientations, as shown in Figure 1, and the Benchy boat (Figure 2), which is a common model to determine the quality of the overhangs and other challenging shapes in 3D printing. At FTPO, samples were printed using the Tumaker BIG FOOT PRO 500 DUAL 3D printer and Creality Ender 3 with SuperSlicer_2.5.59.13 slicing software employed. The nozzle had a diameter of 0.4 mm. Benchy was 3D printed with 10% infill, while 100% infill was used for flexural specimens, as per ISO 178. Printing parameters were shared among the partners. The quality of the prints was investigated using a Keyence VHX-7000 digital optical microscope with 20x magnification.

Figure 1: The positioning of a perpendicular printed flexural specimen on the left and a parallel one on the right on the build plate of the 3D printer

Figure 2: 3D model of the Benchy boat

For ABS the bed was sprayed with 3DLAC to promote adhesion, while packing tape was used for 3D printing of PP. The parameters used were shared among the partners to ensure they were as similar as possible, and these are presented in Table 2. Minor adaptations to the parameters had to be made for the HT 90 and MK4 V2 systems, as presented.

Table 2: 3D printing parameters

Parameters	Value			
	PP	ABS	HT90/MK V2 - PP	HT90/MK V2 - ABS
Nozzle temperature	250 °C	240 °C	245 °C	240 °C
Bed temperature	80 °C	110 °C	0 °C	90 °C
Infill	100 %	100 %	100 %	100 %
Layer height	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.2 mm
Speed	20 mm/s	40 mm/s	10 mm/s	200 mm/s
Travel speed	150 mm/s	150 mm/s	100 mm/s	200 mm/s
Fill pattern	rectilinear	rectilinear	rectilinear	rectilinear
Infill angle	45 °	45 °	45 °	45 °
Perimeters	2	2	2	2
Surface	Packing tape	3DLAC	Elmer's Disappearing Purple Glue	Elmer's Disappearing Purple Glue

Flexural tests were conducted according to ISO 178 on the Shimadzu AG-X plus equipped with a load cell of maximum 10 kN, at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min and span width of 64 mm. For the evaluation of the results, the TrapeziumX software, Version 1.3.1, was used. Five replicates for each sample were tested. Samples were 10 mm wide and 4 mm thick.

Overprinting

For overprinting, modified vitrimers and vitrimer composites were prepared by reactive extrusion and upscaled; they are presented in Table 3. Reactive extrusion was carried out using the LabTech LTE 20-44 twin-screw extruder (Figure 3). Reactive extrusion was performed with 50 min⁻¹ screw rotations to reduce throughput and give the components more time to react. The temperature profile was set to drop from 230 °C at the die to 205 °C at the hopper for ABS, and PP had a similar decreasing temperature profile with 190 °C at the nozzle and 165 °C at the hopper. The compounding of vitrimer composites was done in the second round of extrusion, which was performed at the same temperature settings with screw rotations of 400 min⁻¹ to promote the dispersion of the filler, namely glass beads and milled carbon fibre.

Figure 3: LabTech LTE 20-44 twin-screw extruder

Table 3: Materials prepared by reactive extrusion

Sample	Composition
PPMAH	Exxelor PO1015 from Exxon Chemical
PPMAHCF	PPMAH with 20 wt.% of milled carbon fibre (Milled carbon fibre powder from Easy Composites Ltd)
PPV4	Exxelor PO1015 and 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 Zn(acac) ₂ equiv MAH
PPV4CF	PPV4 with 20 wt.% of milled carbon fibre (Milled carbon fibre powder from Easy Composites Ltd)
ABSM AH	Graftabond ABS MAH 05025CA from Graft Polymer d.o.o.
ABSV4	ABS MAH 05025CA and 1:1 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 Zn(acac) ₂ equiv MAH
ABSV4GB	ABSV4 with 20 wt.% of glass beads (Glass beads for blasting 1-50 μm from Microbeads AG)
ABSV4CF	ABSV4 with 20 wt.% of milled carbon fibre (Milled carbon fibre powder from Easy Composites Ltd)

Injection moulding of the prepared upscaled compounds was carried out on the Krauss Maffei CX 50-180 injection moulding machine (Figure 4) with the processing parameters listed in Table 4. The injection moulding process was used to produce test specimens in sizes according to the ISO 178, ISO 179, and ISO 527 (type 1BA) standards from all the materials listed in Table 3 for characterization purposes, as well as plates for overprinting from PPMAH and PPV4. Plates were 60 x 60 mm and 2 mm in thickness and were used in T1.4 and T1.5.

Figure 4: Krauss Maffei CX 50-180 injection moulding machine

Table 4: Injection moulding parameters

Processing parameter	Value - PP	Value - ABS
Temperature profile (nozzle to hopper) (°C)	170, 175, 170, 165, 160	230, 235, 230, 225, 220
Mould temperature (°C)	30	60
Metering stroke (mm)	Set to 98 % of product fill without holding pressure	Set to 98 % of product fill without holding pressure
Decompression (mm)	2	2
Screw angular velocity (min ⁻¹)	60	60
Backpressure (MPa)	2.0	2.0
Injection velocity (mm/s)	50; 20 - last 1 mm	50; 20 - last 1 mm
Switch-over point (mm)	8	8
Packing pressure (MPa)	80 % of injection pressure	80 % of injection pressure
Packing time (s)	5	5
Rest cooling time (s)	15	15

Material properties were evaluated with DSC, TGA, DMA, stress relaxation, tensile and flexural test, and Charpy impact test.

DSC was performed in the temperature range from 25 °C to 200 °C. All measurements consisted of 2 heating and cooling cycles with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 ml/min. The calorimeter was a Mettler Toledo DSC 2 (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Differential Scanning Calorimeter Mettler Toledo DSC 2

The TGA was performed using a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+ thermogravimetric analyser (Figure 6). The method consisted of a 5-minute isothermal segment at 25 °C, followed by heating from 25 °C to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 ml/min. At 600 °C, the atmosphere was switched to oxygen at a flow rate of 20 ml/min, and heating continued up to 900 °C.

Figure 6: Thermogravimetric analyser Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+

The DMA experiments were carried out using the Perkin Elmer dynamic mechanical analyser, DMA 8000 (Figure 7), with a heating rate of 2 °C/min, a frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 0.01 mm. PP-based samples were measured up to 165 °C, and ABS-based samples up to 175 °C, both in dual cantilever clamping mode.

Figure 7: Dynamic Mechanical analyser DMA 8000 Perkin Elmer

The tensile tests were performed by the ISO 527-1 standard on the Shimadzu AG - X Plus (Figure 8) universal testing machine, equipped with a 10 kN load cell. The shape of the specimen was 1BA. Flexural tests were performed on the same machine according to ISO 178.

Figure 8: Universal testing machine Shimadzu AG - X Plus

Vitrimer composites (PPMAHCF, PPV4CF, ABSV4GB and ABSV4CF) were used for the production of filaments. PPMAH and PPV4CF for purposes of overprinting in T1.4 and ABSV4GB and ABSV4CF for overprinting in T1.5 of WP1. Filaments were produced employing the production line AFE28 of Suzhou Aifuer Machinery CO., LTD (Figure 9), which was acquired in the scope of IPPT_TWINN project was used for filament production. The single-screw extruder SJ25/28 of the line is equipped with a screw made of 38CrMoALA. The screw has a diameter of 25 mm and an L/D ratio of 28:1. Its maximal operating screw speed is 72 min^{-1} , and it provides a production capacity of 3–5 kg per hour. The extruder produces filament with a diameter ranging from 1.75 to 3 mm, achieving a tolerance of $\pm 0.02\text{--}0.03 \text{ mm}$. PP-based filaments were produced at $170 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the nozzle, and ABS-based filaments were produced at $230 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the nozzle; both were extruded at screw velocity of 30 min^{-1} .

Figure 9: Filament production line AFE28 of Suzhou Aifuer Machinery CO., LTD

PPMAHCF and PPV4CF ribs were printed on the PP-based substrates using Tumaker BF 500 Dual 3D printer from IT3D Group (Figure 10), equipped with two printing heads, one for filament printing and the second for direct 3D printing from polymer granulate. In this case, only the filament feed extruder was used for printing of produced filaments at 180 °C and 200 °C at a 0.4 mm nozzle. FTPO printed the ribs at both temperatures at the nozzle, IWK printed them at 180 °C, and the rest of the partners printed the ribs at 200 °C. Printing speed was 10 mm/s, infill was 100 %, and the build plate was heated to 75 °C. Printing parameters of the ribs are summarised in Table 5.

Figure 10: Tumaker BF 500 Dual 3D printer

Table 5: Printing parameters of PPMHCF and PPV4CF ribs

Parameter	Values
Nozzle temperature	180 °C & 200 °C
Bed temperature	25 °C
Infill	100 %
Layer height	0.3 mm
Printing speed	30 mm/s
Travel speed	150 mm/s
Fill pattern	rectilinear
Infill angle	45 °
Perimeters	2

The overprinted substrates (Figures 12 and 13) were tested for peel strength; a list of prepared samples is presented in Table 6. Half of the samples were annealed at 150 °C for 6 h in a vacuum oven. The peel test was carried out on the Shimadzu AG-X Plus universal testing machine, with the standard measurement consisting of a preliminary test at 1 mm/min up to 3 N of load, followed by 50 mm/min until the break. 10 repetitions were measured for each sample due to high standard deviations. For overprinting, Tumaker BF 500 Dual 3D was used at FTPO, Prusa MK4 at IWK and AITIIP, MethodX at BME, and PCCL used Creatbot F430.

Figure 11: PPV4 plate overprinted with PPV4CF

Figure 12: Drafting sketch of the sample

Table 6: Overprinted samples list

Sample	Plate	Rib	Annealing
PPMAH-PPMAH	PPMAH	PPMAHCF	-
PPMAH-PPV4	PPMAH	PPV4CF	-
PPV4-PPMAH	PPV4	PPMAHCF	-
PPV4-PPV4	PPV4	PPV4CF	-
PPMAH-PPMAH - A	PPMAH	PPMAHCF	6 h at 150 °C
PPMAH-PPV4 - A	PPMAH	PPV4CF	6 h at 150 °C
PPV4-PPMAH - A	PPV4	PPMAHCF	6 h at 150 °C
PPV4-PPV4 - A	PPV4	PPV4CF	6 h at 150 °C

Experimental results

Round Robin test

Dimensional accuracy

Dimensions of 3D printed samples are presented in Table 7-10. According to the standard ISO 178 the dimensions should be 10x4 mm and 80 mm in length. Dimensions of 3D printed samples were analysed, and it is suggested by the results that while acceptable dimensions are produced by most printers, marginally better dimensional accuracy and consistency are provided by ABS material compared to PP. Dimensional accuracy is also influenced by the orientation of prints, with width measurements generally being closer to the target 10 mm for parallel prints. High shrinkage of PP, which is more prone to warping, could be a possible cause of dimensional inaccuracy. Samples printed with Ender presented the biggest difference in dimensions. It is thought that the problem was under-extrusion.

Table 7: Dimensions of PP samples printed parallel to the build plate

Printer	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)
PP-Tumaker	10.54	3.87
PP-Ender	9.99	3.30
PP-QIDI	9.98	3.93
PP-PrusaXL	9.87	4.02
PP-MK4	9.90	3.90
PP-X1C	9.95	3.93
PP-MethodX	9.98	4.10
PP-X1C V2	9.90	3.88
PP-HT	9.85	4.00
PP-MK4 V2	10.05	3.85
Average	10.00	3.88
St. deviation	0.20	0.22

Table 8: Dimensions of ABS samples printed parallel to the build plate

Printer	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)
ABS-Tumaker	10.16	3.97
ABS-Ender	10.3	3.8
ABS-QIDI	9.96	4.13
ABS-PrusaXL	9.92	3.99
ABS-MK4	9.95	3.88
ABS-X1C	9.86	4
ABS-MethodX	10.05	4.25
ABS-X1C V2	9.90	4
ABS-HT	9.98	4
ABS-MK4 V2	10.00	4
Average	10.01	4.00
St. deviation	0.13	0.12

Table 9: Dimensions of PP samples printed perpendicular to the build plate

Printer	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)
PP-Tumaker	10.05	4.05
PP-Ender	9.85	3.76
PP-QIDI	10.00	3.96
PP-PrusaXL	9.90	3.90
PP-MK4	9.90	3.97
PP-X1C	10.00	4.00
PP-MethodX	9.90	4.02
PP-X1C V2	9.82	3.92
PP-HT	9.97	3.96
PP-MK4 V2	9.87	3.93
Average	9.93	3.95
St. deviation	0.07	0.08

Table 10: Dimensions of ABS samples printed perpendicular to the build plate

Printer	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)
ABS-Tumaker	10.16	3.97
ABS-Ender	10.3	3.8
ABS-QIDI	9.96	4.13
ABS-PrusaXL	9.92	3.99
ABS-MK4	9.95	3.88
ABS-X1C	9.86	4
ABS-MethodX	10.10	4.15
ABS-X1C V2	10.00	4
ABS-HT	10.20	4
ABS-MK4 V2	10.10	4
Average	10.06	3.99
St. deviation	0.14	0.10

Flexural tests – according to ISO 178

Results of the flexural test are presented in Tables 11 – 14. The highest flexural strength was measured by X1C (11.90 MPa). The flexural strain at the point of flexural strength ranges between 6.80 % and 7.93 %, with the highest value being exhibited by MK4. It is implied by the findings that superior performance in terms of rigidity and strength for parallel prints of PP is exhibited by X1C and Tumaker. The highest flexural modulus was measured by X1C (0.54 GPa), and the highest flexural strength is noted by X1C (12.27 MPa). Data pertaining to flexural strain at the flexural break are not included because the sample did not break during the measurement. In general, the most robust and rigid among the perpendicular specimens is PP-X1C-perpendicular.

The highest flexural modulus (2.46 GPa) was registered by ABS-Tumaker-parallel, thus it is designated as the most rigid specimen. The greatest flexural strength was noted in ABS-Tumaker-parallel (75.04 MPa). The range of flexural strain at flexural strength values fluctuates between 4.51% and 5.06%. The highest flexural strain at flexural break (10.45%) was recorded by ABS-MK4-

parallel, indicating its capacity to sustain greater deformation before failure. The most favorable overall performance is exhibited by ABS-Tumaker-parallel.

For ABS perpendicular prints, HT is characterized by the highest flexural modulus (2.24 GPa) with a flexural strength of 74.62 MPa. The flexural strain at flexural strength varies from 0.97% to 5.70%, with MethodX reflecting the maximum strain. MK4 demonstrates the highest flexural strain at flexural break (10.14%), rendering it the most ductile. Overall, HT showcases the optimal equilibrium of rigidity and strength.

In the context of PP, the most favourable mechanical attributes are illustrated by X1C (both parallel and perpendicular). Regarding ABS, the highest levels of strength and rigidity are displayed by both Tumaker and HT. The contrast between parallel and perpendicular printing orientations is underscored by the fact that superior performance is generally exhibited by parallel specimens, particularly in terms of flexural modulus and strength. The significant impact of printer choice on mechanical properties was shown by these results, with certain printers excelling at specific materials and orientations. The necessity of considering part orientation during the design process for 3D printed components is further emphasized by the substantial variation between parallel and perpendicular properties.

Table 11: Flexural test – collected results for PP parallel

Sample	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural strain at flexural strength (%)
PP-Tumaker-parallel	0.43 ± 0.02	11.32 ± 0.38	6.80 ± 0.30
PP-Ender-parallel	0.16 ± 0.02	5.18 ± 0.37	5.55 ± 0.69
PP-QIDI-parallel	0.40 ± 0.02	11.69 ± 0.36	7.31 ± 0.33
PP-PrusaXL-parallel	0.23 ± 0.01	7.05 ± 0.70	7.16 ± 0.29
PP-MK4-parallel	0.32 ± 0.02	8.95 ± 0.78	6.93 ± 0.39
PP-X1C-parallel	0.42 ± 0.02	11.90 ± 0.14	7.39 ± 0.17
PP-MethodX-parallel	0.34 ± 0.01	9.22 ± 0.17	6.82 ± 0.53
PP-X1C V2-parallel	0.35 ± 0.01	10.05 ± 0.13	7.35 ± 0.20
PP-HT-parallel	0.31 ± 0.00	9.60 ± 0.24	7.37 ± 0.36
PP-MK4 V2-parallel	0.36 ± 0.03	10.01 ± 0.25	6.47 ± 0.21

Table 12: Flexural test – collected results for PP perpendicular

Sample	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural strain at flexural strength (%)
PP-Tumaker-perpendicular	0.19 ± 0.01	6.71 ± 0.11	7.32 ± 0.40
PP-Ender-perpendicular	0.09 ± 0.00	3.41 ± 0.07	5.86 ± 0.37
PP-QIDI-perpendicular	0.28 ± 0.01	8.68 ± 0.07	7.18 ± 0.62
PP-PrusaXL-perpendicular	0.18 ± 0.00	6.22 ± 0.03	6.82 ± 0.14
PP-MK4-perpendicular	0.20 ± 0.00	6.84 ± 0.05	6.96 ± 0.27
PP-X1C-perpendicular	0.28 ± 0.02	8.58 ± 0.22	7.05 ± 0.23
PP-MethodX-perpendicular	0.54 ± 0.01	13.26 ± 0.06	6.98 ± 0.10
PP-X1C V2-perpendicular	0.36 ± 0.01	12.27 ± 0.04	7.20 ± 0.19
PP-HT-perpendicular	0.45 ± 0.01	12.50 ± 0.07	7.18 ± 0.11
PP-MK4 V2-perpendicular	0.41 ± 0.05	12.21 ± 0.80	7.32 ± 0.37

Table 13: Flexural test – collected results for ABS parallel

Sample	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural strain at flexural strength (%)	Flexural strain at flexural break (%)
ABS-Tumaker-parallel	2.46 ± 0.05	75.04 ± 0.19	4.85 ± 0.18	6.76 ± 0.64
ABS-Ender-parallel	2.09 ± 0.07	66.86 ± 1.09	4.86 ± 0.08	7.81 ± 1.44
ABS-QIDI-parallel	2.13 ± 0.05	68.47 ± 0.88	5.11 ± 0.11	8.19 ± 0.46
ABS-PrusaXL-parallel	2.32 ± 0.03	69.81 ± 0.39	4.89 ± 0.06	7.70 ± 0.96
ABS-MK4-parallel	2.32 ± 0.09	70.43 ± 2.20	4.83 ± 0.08	8.43 ± 0.20
ABS-X1C-parallel	2.25 ± 0.01	67.12 ± 0.42	4.88 ± 0.08	7.62 ± 0.75
ABS-MethodX-parallel	1.83 ± 0.04	61.77 ± 1.13	5.61 ± 0.14	10.45 ± 2.24
ABS-X1C V2-parallel	2.28 ± 0.03	69.01 ± 0.44	5.06 ± 0.06	8.67 ± 1.17
ABS-HT-parallel	2.26 ± 0.05	67.94 ± 1.78	4.76 ± 0.10	7.70 ± 1.36
ABS-MK4 V2-parallel	2.13 ± 0.04	67.15 ± 0.52	5.02 ± 0.06	9.07 ± 1.37

Table 14: Flexural test – collected results for ABS perpendicular

Sample	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural strain at flexural strength (%)	Flexural strain at flexural break (%)
ABS-Tumaker-perpendicular	1.76 ± 0.15	17.95 ± 5.35	0.97 ± 0.25	0.97 ± 0.25
ABS-Ender-perpendicular	1.94 ± 0.05	22.44 ± 2.95	1.10 ± 0.15	1.10 ± 0.15
ABS-QIDI-perpendicular	1.89 ± 0.04	44.79 ± 1.38	2.55 ± 0.12	2.62 ± 0.20
ABS-PrusaXL-perpendicular	1.79 ± 0.05	26.01 ± 2.84	1.36 ± 0.14	1.35 ± 0.14
ABS-MK4-perpendicular	1.73 ± 0.03	35.17 ± 3.75	1.97 ± 0.22	1.98 ± 0.22
ABS-X1C-perpendicular	1.80 ± 0.06	29.87 ± 2.84	1.60 ± 0.20	1.60 ± 0.20
ABS-MethodX-perpendicular	1.92 ± 0.11	70.21 ± 1.45	5.70 ± 0.23	9.83 ± 2.08
ABS-X1C V2-perpendicular	2.02 ± 0.07	69.77 ± 0.27	5.19 ± 0.14	8.82 ± 1.35
ABS-HT-perpendicular	2.24 ± 0.06	74.62 ± 0.22	4.69 ± 0.03	9.37 ± 0.48
ABS-MK4 V2-perpendicular	2.17 ± 0.13	70.40 ± 0.55	4.75 ± 0.19	10.14 ± 1.87

Microscopy

For the accuracy of printers, we analyzed the hull, which should be evenly round and smooth, and the layer lines shouldn't be too prominent. We examined the underside to check the quality of the first layer. Then we looked at the details on the Benchy's deck house and chimney to analyse overhangs, bridging, and other fine features. The differences between printers are shown in Figures 14-25. After analysing the quality of printed samples, it was concluded that ABS is easier to print than PP. Similar results with ABS were obtained on different 3D printers, but very different results with PP were achieved.

Generally good quality, with slightly less consistent layer lines, was demonstrated by Tumaker. Small artefacts and irregularities are shown on the deckhouse edges. Decent formation, but with minor imperfections can be seen in the chimney. Good shape with minimal deformation is maintained by circular features. A good definition with only minor edge irregularities is displayed by portholes.

Noticeable inconsistencies across different features are shown by Ender. Visible artefacts in the layer pattern are displayed by the surface texture. Evident stringing issues are exhibited by the deckhouse.

Notable surface irregularities and poor layer adhesion are shown by the chimney. Significant stringing inside the opening is exhibited by the chimney. Acceptable definition, but lacking precision is possessed by portholes.

High-quality prints with very consistent, uniform layer lines were produced by HT 90. One of the cleanest, most well-defined deckhouse edges is produced. An excellent chimney structure with minimal defects is featured. Good shape is maintained by circular features, though slightly less perfect than top performers. Slightly less circular portholes, but with clean edges, are presented. It is counted among the top three performers.

Minor surface imperfections in flat areas are shown by Method X. Some shape irregularities are possessed by the deckhouse arch. Good detail overall, with occasional imperfections, is shown by the chimney feature. A good circular shape for the smokestack is maintained. Some deformation in hole shape is exhibited by the porthole.

Excellent surface quality with very smooth, even layer lines was displayed by PrusaXL. Small artefacts on the edge, but generally good definition is shown by the doorway. Very clean definition with consistent layer lines is possessed by the chimney. A good circular shape is maintained by the smokestack. Good hole definition with minimal irregularities is shown by portholes.

Major quality problems across most features are demonstrated by QIDI. Inconsistent layer lines are shown by the surface texture. Obvious edge irregularities and blobbing are possessed by the doorway. Serious deformation and extreme blobbing are exhibited by the chimney. Circular features like the smokestack are significantly melted or deformed. Irregular shapes with edge problems are shown by portholes.

Minor surface imperfections in flat areas are shown by Method X. Some shape irregularities are possessed by the doorway arch. Good detail overall, with occasional imperfections, is displayed by the chimney feature. A good circular shape for the smokestack is maintained. Some deformation in the hole shape is exhibited by the porthole. Solid middle-tier performance with occasional quality issues is delivered.

Two samples with X1C were printed, one on PCCL in Leoben and second one on BME in Budapest. Two very different results were obtained. Consistently uniform layer lines and well-defined features are shown by one. Excellent surface quality with minimal imperfections is displayed. Minimal stringing is possessed by the deckhouse, the chimney structure is clean with uniform surfaces, and precise shapes with clean edges are maintained by circular features. Accurate details with good dimensional stability are produced. Significant quality issues across multiple features are shown by the other one. Less uniform layer lines with waviness are possessed by the surface. Noticeable irregularities and blobbing are displayed by doorway edges. Severe defects with extreme blobbing and deformation are shown by the chimney. Proper circular openings in the smokestack were not maintained, showing significant melting. Poor uniformity with edge issues is possessed by portholes.

The same was experienced with MK4. One sample was printed in IWK in Switzerland and in AITIIP in Spain. But similar results were achieved here. Excellent surface quality with uniform layer lines is displayed. Some visible artefacts are shown by the surface. A little stringing issue inside the deckhouse area is present. An excellent chimney structure is featured. Stringing and irregularities inside the

opening are shown by the chimney. Good definition, but with minor edge issues, is possessed by portholes.

Figure 13: Microscope - PP hull under 20x magnification

Figure 14: Microscope - PP deck house under 20x magnification

Figure 15: Microscope - PP chimney under 20x magnification

Figure 16: Microscope - PP chimney from the top under 20x magnification

Figure 17: Microscope - PP porthole under 20x magnification

Figure 18: Microscope - PP backside under 20x magnification

Figure 19: Microscope - ABS hull under 20x magnification

Figure 20: Microscope - ABS deck house under 20x magnification

Figure 21: Microscope - ABS chimney under 20x magnification

Figure 22: Microscope - ABS chimney from the top under 20x magnification

Figure 23: Microscope - ABS porthole under 20x magnification

Figure 24: Microscope - ABS backside under 20x magnification

The best consistency across all features, which is also the most important part, was demonstrated by HT 90, MK4, Method X and Tumaker. The best quality with one of the samples and one of the worst qualities with the second sample was exhibited by X1C. The worst quality of 3D print samples was by Ender and QIDI.

In conclusion, generally different parameters are used by each middle- or high-end tier printer. It is shown that parameters must be modified according to the printer to obtain the best quality part.

Characterization of upscaled materials and overprinting

Grafted PP and ABS (PPMAH and ABSMAH), and vitrimerized materials (PPV4, ABSV4 and their composites) were prepared, injection moulded, and 3D printed for overprinting (T1.4), and demonstrator production (T1.5). They were synthesised via reactive extrusion, composites were prepared by subsequent compounding, and all of them were injection moulded for testing.

Differential scanning calorimetry

DSC results (Table 15) of PP-based vitrimer formulations (PPV4, PPV4-CF) show clearly reduced melting and crystallization temperatures compared to PPMAH, indicating that the vitrimer network disrupts the crystalline structure. Both ΔH_m and ΔH_c are significantly lower, confirming a reduced degree of crystallinity. The presence of carbon fibre further decreases the enthalpy values due to filler dilution. Overall, the DSC data show that vitrimer chemistry noticeably limits chain mobility and crystallization in PP.

Table 15: Gathered DSC results of PP-based specimen

Sample	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	T_c (°C)	ΔH_c (J/g)
PPMAH	152.23	54.33	123.59	52.09
PPMAH-CF	151.97	46.12	122.84	39.18
PPV4	146.63	50.37	109.70	50.13
PPV4-CF	147.74	39.61	110.13	38.49

For ABS-based formulations, T_g remains almost unchanged across all samples, but Δc_p decreases steadily from ABSMAH to ABSV4 and further in the filled composites. The lower Δc_p values indicate reduced segmental mobility and tighter network constraints introduced by the vitrimer chemistry. Fillers further restrict mobility. In summary, vitrimer modification affects the amorphous-phase response of ABS, even though T_g itself remains stable.

Table 16: Gathered DSC results of ABS specimen

Sample	T_g (°C)	Δc_p (J/gK)
ABSMAH	101.79	0.236
ABSV4	101.37	0.173
ABSV4-GB	101.16	0.107
ABSV4-CF	100.17	0.079

Thermogravimetric analysis

The TGA curves (Figure 25) of PP-based materials (PPMAH, PPMAH-CF, PPV4, PPV4-CF) show that all formulations exhibit similar thermal stability in the initial degradation region. Degradation temperature with vitrimerization seems to increase compared to neat materials; however, with reinforcement, the

trend is decreasing. Overall, PP vitrimer formulations remain thermally stable up to typical processing temperatures and above.

Figure 25: TGA curves of PP-based specimen

Figure 26 presents the TGA curves of the ABS-based materials (ABSMAH, ABSV4, ABSV4GB, ABSV4CF) that exhibit nearly identical thermal degradation behaviour, with major mass loss occurring around 415 °C. The introduction of vitrimer chemistry does not meaningfully alter the degradation temperature or rate of degradation. Composites containing glass beads or carbon fibre demonstrate increased residual mass at high temperatures, consistent with the inorganic filler content. The results confirm the comparable thermal stability of ABS-based CAN formulations to standard ABS-based materials.

Figure 26: TGA curves of ABS-based specimen

Tensile and Flexural properties

Tensile Modulus and Strength results that are presented in Figure 27 indicate an increase after the vitrimerization. Fibre-filled variants (PPMAH-CF, PPV4-CF, ABSV4-GB, ABSV4-CF) exhibit substantially

higher stiffness and strength, reflecting the dominating influence of reinforcement rather than CAN chemistry.

Figure 27: Tensile Modulus (left) and Strength (right) of upscaled specimen

Flexural testing results (Figure 28) demonstrate similar trends to tensile testing. Neat vitrimer formulations show flexural properties comparable to, or slightly higher than, the unmodified matrix polymers. Fibre-reinforced variants significantly outperform neat materials, confirming that reinforcement is the primary driver of improved stiffness and strength.

Figure 28: Flexural Modulus and Flexural Strength of up-scaled specimen

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

For PP-based materials, the storage modulus (Figure 29) declines with temperature in characteristic PP behaviour. The vitrimer-modified PPV4 and PPV4-CF show slightly higher storage moduli. However, overall modulus levels remain close to PPMAH and PPMAH-CF. Reinforced samples again exhibit higher modulus due to carbon fibre content, not CAN chemistry.

Figure 29: Storage Modulus versus Temperature of PP-based samples

In the rubbery plateau region, the PP-based vitrimer formulations (PPV4 and PPV4-CF) show clear and significant increases in storage modulus compared to their maleic-anhydride-modified counterparts (PPMaH and PPMaH-CF). This pronounced difference indicates that the dynamic covalent network introduced through vitrimer chemistry effectively restricts molecular mobility at elevated temperatures, resulting in a noticeably stiffer material response in the rubbery state.

The higher modulus observed for PPV4 and PPV4CF demonstrates that vitrimer crosslinking contributes meaningfully to maintaining structural integrity when the polymer is above its melting or softening range. Although reinforcement with carbon fibre still has the strongest absolute effect on stiffness, the vitrimer network itself above the melting temperature contributes more indicated by clear surpass of PPMaHCF by PPV4 above 150 °C.

These results and stress relaxation results from D1.3 (activation energy of 94 kJ/mol) for PPV4 system, resulting in T_v of 52 °C) confirm that, at least in the rubbery regime, vitrimer chemistry has a substantial influence on the thermo-mechanical behaviour of thermoplastic-based CAN systems.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of ABS-based vitrimer formulations (Figure 30) shows how the storage modulus decreases with increasing temperature over the glass transition region. ABSV4-GB and ABSV4-CF show higher modulus due to reinforcement. The vitrimer network does produce a modulus increase over the whole temperature range compared to ABSMaH.

Figure 30: Storage modulus versus temperature of ABS-based samples

In the rubbery plateau region (Figure 33), vitrimer-modified ABS samples maintain higher modulus up to higher temperature values than the neat ABSMAH material, which falls to practically 0 at 170 °C, suggesting the presence of a crosslinked structure in the network **and with dynamic covalent bonds based on complementary stress relaxation results presented in D1.3 where activation energy of 151 kJ/mol and T_v of 156 °C were determined for the ABSV4.** Fibre-filled ABS samples show substantially higher modulus due to filler effects.

Charpy impact test

Impact testing results (Figure 31) show that vitrimer-modified PP composite exhibits increased impact toughness. No claims could be made comparing grafted PP and PPV4, since none of them broke under 5 J weight. ABS samples generally exhibit lower impact toughness than their unmodified counterparts, indicating increased brittleness. The reinforcing fillers (CF, GB) further reduce impact resistance, as expected. CAN chemistry does not enhance toughness in the case of ABS.

Figure 31: Impact toughness of PP-based samples on the left and ABS-based samples on the right

Peel test

Peel testing results of samples prepared at FTPO (Figure 32) show that increasing the printing temperature from 180 °C to 200 °C slightly improves adhesion for both PPMAHCF and PPV4CF samples, mainly because the predominant failure mechanism is rib failure due to the low strength of the ribs. However, the absolute peel strengths remain relatively low. The expected benefit from dynamic bond exchange in CAN materials is limited or cannot be characterized due to high standard deviations that are recorded employing this type of substrate and overprinted rib.

Figure 32: Peel Strengths determined for FTPO samples printed at 180 °C on the left and at 200 °C on the right

Inter-partner comparison of peel strength results (Figure 33) shows variations in peel strength, influenced by printer setup, temperature stability, and material handling. Overall, peel strengths are in the range between 1 MPa and 6 MPa and do not demonstrate a clear advantage of vitrimer-modified materials compared to baseline systems, nor the advantage of annealing procedures. Across different partners, the performance of CAN-based materials remains inconsistent, further indicating that their bonding improvements are limited under practical processing conditions. The main challenge is presented by high standard deviations, which are apparently consistent with the procedure of overprinting, as standard deviations are high regardless of the 3D printer used or who prepared the samples.

Figure 33: Comparison of Peel Strengths of overprinted samples produced by partners

In Deliverable 1.1, we used two different grades of PP for overmoulding substrates. Peel strength of 5-12.5 MPa was measured on samples overmoulded at 180 °C, increasing to 10-15 MPa at 200 °C [7]. These results suggest that peel strength can be increased for overprinting, as lower strength values of 0.2-6 MPa and 1-15 MPa were achieved at 180 °C and 200 °C temperatures, respectively. Increasing the printing temperature and adding fibres into the material increased the peel strength for both overmoulding and overprinting. Similar failure modes were observed in the samples produced by overmoulding and overprinting. In most cases, the sample broke at the interface; however, in some instances, if the rib broke, the interface bonding was stronger than the rib's load-bearing capacity. The cause of the failure is presumably different; in the case of the overmoulded samples, the interfacial bonding was higher than the material's tensile strength. In the case of the overprinted samples, the adhesion at the interface was greater than the adhesion of the rib layers. Standard deviations are high in both cases, as hybrid bonding results are highly sensitive to processing reproducibility, resulting in high experimental noise that can dominate moderate material or process modifications. In Task 1.1, mechanical interlocking was successfully employed to enhance the peel strength of overprinted parts; this could significantly improve peel strength in the case of vitrimer-modified material for future research.

Related publications

This chapter presents summaries of publications related to or derived from the project published in the given timeframe.

1. Title of the publication: Novel Coupled Simulation Method and Comprehensive Metrology to Enhance the Application of Prototype Injection Moulds³

Our research article investigates coupled simulation methods and comprehensive metrology for additively manufactured prototype injection moulds, providing an essential scientific foundation for understanding the thermal and mechanical behaviour of polymeric mould inserts used in hybrid manufacturing processes relevant to Deliverable D1.4 of the IPPT_TWINN project.

Our key contribution is the development of a novel coupled simulation approach that combines injection moulding simulation with finite element thermal and mechanical analyses to model the operational characteristics of polymeric mould inserts. In D1.4, we used injection moulding to produce

substrates (PPMAH and PPV4 plates) and test specimens from vitrimer-modified materials, where understanding mould behaviour during processing is critical for achieving reproducible material properties and consistent substrate quality for overprinting experiments.

Our research demonstrates that the low thermal conductivity of polymeric mould materials (0.2 W/(m·K) for VeroWhite photopolymer, compared to 14–20 W/(m·K) for tool steels) results in localised heating of the cavity surface by up to 30°C during the moulding cycle. This finding is directly relevant for D1.4, where we processed temperature-sensitive vitrimer formulations (PPV4, ABSV4) that exhibit dynamic covalent bond exchange behaviour dependent on thermal history. The cavity surface temperature variations we characterised help explain the importance of controlled processing conditions for achieving consistent vitrimer network formation.

We employ similar equipment and comparable processing conditions used in D1.4. Our injection moulding experiments were performed on an Arburg Allrounder Advance 270S 400-170 machine with a 30 mm screw diameter. We used polypropylene (Tipplén H145F) with melt temperature of 190°C and 2 mm thick plate specimens.

Our comprehensive analysis of strain gauge measurements, cavity pressure monitoring, and thermal imaging provides critical methodology for D1.4's investigation of hybrid manufacturing processes. The DMA characterisation approach we applied for VeroWhite photopolymer (where storage modulus drops from 2200 MPa at room temperature to 100 MPa at 65°C due to glass transition) contrasts with the vitrimer behaviour observed in D1.4, where PPV4 maintains significantly higher storage modulus in the rubbery plateau region above 150°C compared to non-vitrimer PPMAH. This difference confirms the presence of dynamic covalent networks in vitrimer formulations—while conventional polymers lose structural integrity above T_g , vitrimers retain dimensional stability due to their crosslinked architecture with exchangeable bonds.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4028/p-q56eQa>

Freely accessible at:

[1946 open ISCAMÉ 2024 Novel coupled simulation method Krizma Suplicz.pdf](#)

2. Title of the publication: Prediction of the Thermal Degradation–Induced Colour Change of ABS Products as a Function of Temperature and Titanium Dioxide Content ¹

Our research article investigates the thermal degradation–induced colour change of acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) products as a function of temperature and titanium dioxide content, providing an essential scientific foundation for understanding the long-term appearance stability of ABS-based materials used in Deliverable D1.4 of the IPPT_TWINN project.

Our key contribution is the development of a robust predictive model based on the time–temperature superposition (tTS) principle and CIELAB colour space that enables estimation of long-term colour change in TiO₂-doped ABS products. In D1.4, we used ABS-based vitrimer formulations (ABSMAH, ABSV4, ABSV4GB, ABSV4CF) for hybrid manufacturing applications, where thermal exposure during processing and end-use can significantly affect product appearance. Our model, validated through 1600 hours of measurements, achieves average colour differences below 1.5 at application temperatures (below 80°C)—smaller than the just noticeable difference (JND) in the CIELAB colour space.

Our research demonstrates that above approximately 3 wt% TiO₂ content, colour retention of ABS specimens can no longer be improved by increasing TiO₂ concentration. This finding is directly relevant for D1.4, where we produced ABS-based composites with various filler contents (20 wt% glass beads, 20 wt% carbon fibre). Understanding the saturation behaviour of stabilising additives helps optimise formulation strategies for vitrimer composites intended for hybrid overprinting applications.

Importantly, we employ identical processing conditions and characterisation methods used in D1.4. Our injection-moulded ABS plates were produced at comparable temperature profiles (225–240°C) and

mould temperatures (30°C) to those used for ABSV4 substrates in D1.4 (230–235°C melt temperature, 60°C mould temperature). We utilise the same thermal analysis approaches (DSC, TGA) employed in D1.4 for material characterisation, ensuring direct comparability of results.

Our comprehensive analysis of ABS thermal degradation kinetics provides critical baseline data for D1.4's investigation of vitrimer-modified ABS systems. The thermal ageing temperatures examined (60–100°C) encompass the processing and application conditions relevant to hybrid manufacturing, where overprinted components may experience elevated temperatures during annealing (150°C for 6 hours in D1.4) or service life. The methodology enables prediction of appearance changes before production, supporting quality control for the demonstrator parts developed in Task 1.5.

Accessible at/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.103505>

3. Title of the publication: Effect of Processing Parameters and Wall Thickness on the Strength of Injection Molded Products ⁴

Our research article investigates how injection moulding processing parameters and wall thickness influence the mechanical properties of polymer components, providing an essential scientific foundation for understanding the injection-moulded substrates used in Deliverable D1.4 of the IPPT_TWINN project.

Our key contribution is demonstrating that wall thickness fundamentally influences the skin-core morphology of injection-moulded parts. At 2 mm thickness—exactly that used for substrates in D1.4—the core layer represents 70-80% of the cross-section, making material properties relatively insensitive to process variations. This finding validates our substrate thickness selection in D1.4 and ensures that bonding strength results reflect interfacial phenomena rather than substrate property variability.

Our research shows that skin layer thickness remains approximately 0.2-0.3 mm regardless of part thickness. Since the overprinted material in D1.4 primarily interacts with this highly oriented surface layer, understanding its formation and properties is critical for predicting interfacial bonding. We demonstrate that this skin layer exhibits significantly different mechanical properties than bulk material due to rapid cooling and molecular orientation effects.

Importantly, we prove that at 2 mm thickness, injection moulding parameters (melt temperature 220-240°C, mould temperature 50-85°C, injection rate 5-40 cm³/s) have minimal effects on mechanical properties, with variations remaining within standard deviation. This confirms that our injection-moulded substrates in D1.4 provide a stable and reproducible platform for overprinting experiments, ensuring that variations in peel strength primarily reflect interfacial bonding differences rather than substrate inconsistencies.

Our comprehensive analysis of ABS mechanical properties at various processing conditions provides critical baseline data for D1.4, which uses similar ABS-based materials (ABSMAH, ABSV4) at comparable temperatures. We employ the same characterization methods (TGA, DSC, DMA) used in D1.4, ensuring direct comparability of results and enabling our findings on base ABS materials to serve as reference points for evaluating vitrimer modification effects.

Accessible at/DOI: [10.3311/PPme.24068](https://doi.org/10.3311/PPme.24068)

4. Title of the publication: Modeling the effect of scale deposition on heat transfer in injection molding ²

Our research article investigates the effect of scale deposition on heat transfer in injection moulding, providing an essential scientific foundation for understanding the cooling efficiency of moulds used in manufacturing substrates for Deliverable D1.4 of the IPPT_TWINN project.

Our key contribution is the development of a universal model that predicts the cooling efficiency of injection moulds while accounting for deposit layer thickness and thermal conductivity. In D1.4, we

used injection moulding to produce substrates and test specimens, where reliable cooling is critical for achieving reproducible material properties. Our research demonstrates that even a 1 mm thick deposit layer with thermal conductivity of 1 W/(mK) reduces cooling efficiency by 10–25%, directly affecting cycle time and temperature distribution on the mould cavity surface.

Our research shows that conformal cooling channels, commonly used in modern moulds manufactured by additive technologies, exhibit greater sensitivity to scale deposition than conventional channels. At 2 mm deposit thickness, conformal cooling efficiency decreases to the level of conventional cooling. This finding is relevant for D1.4, where substrates were injection moulded using the Krauss Maffei CX 50-180 machine, as it emphasizes the importance of cooling system maintenance for achieving consistent substrate quality.

Importantly, we demonstrate how thermal conductivity of the mould material influences sensitivity to deposition. Moulds made from highly conductive materials (e.g., Ampcoloy 88 with conductivity of 230 W/(mK)) better mitigate the negative effects of deposition compared to steel moulds (MS1 with conductivity of 20 W/(mK)). In D1.4, standard steel moulds were used, where control over cooling channel condition is particularly critical for maintaining consistent processing conditions.

Our comprehensive analysis of heat transfer dynamics in cooling systems provides critical data for understanding processing conditions in D1.4, where PPMaH and PPV4 substrates were injection moulded at melt temperature of 170–175 °C and a mould temperature of 30 °C. We employ comparable numerical methods (FEM analysis, cycle-averaged calculations) and materials (PP), enabling direct connection between our findings on cooling efficiency and the reproducibility of substrate properties used for peel strength testing in hybrid structures.

Accessible at/DOI: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-98657-x>

5. The paper titled “Improving inter-layer adhesion in fused filament fabrication additive manufacturing through dynamic covalent chemistry” was submitted to Express Polymer Letters in November and is advancing through the peer-review process, with a revised manuscript in preparation.

This study reports the development of thermoplastic-based vitrimers via reactive extrusion of maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene with an epoxy crosslinker and a transesterification catalyst, as reported in Deliverable 1.4. Material was after initial reactive extrusion reinforced with carbon fibre (CF) to produce CF reinforced vitrimer filaments used for fused filament fabrication, enabling evaluation of interlayer adhesion in FFF produced parts. Spectroscopic and thermomechanical analyses confirmed the formation of a dynamic crosslinked network with β -hydroxyester linkages and a pronounced rubbery plateau. The vitrimer materials showed substantially improved mechanical performance, including up to a 155 % increase in notched Charpy impact strength. Printed vitrimer specimens exhibited enhanced flexural toughness and improved interlayer bonding, attributed to dynamic transesterification during printing. Post-printing thermal annealing preserved toughness and slightly increased flexural strength in vitrimeric specimens, whereas non-vitrimeric materials became embrittled. Overall, vitrimerisation is demonstrated as an effective strategy to improve interlayer adhesion in FFF parts.

Conclusions

The activities carried out in Task 1.4 enabled a comprehensive evaluation of CAN-modified PP- and ABS-based materials in hybrid manufacturing processes combining injection moulding and fused filament fabrication. While the preparation and upscaling of vitrimer and vitrimer-composite formulations were successful, the overall performance of these CAN materials did not meet the initially expected improvements in bonding strength or mechanical behaviour.

The Round Robin study confirmed that printer type and print orientation remain dominant factors influencing dimensional accuracy and flexural performance. ABS materials showed greater stability and inter-partner consistency, whereas PP continued to exhibit significant shrinkage and warping.

Characterization of the upscaled CAN materials revealed measurable network modification, but these structural changes did not consistently translate into improved mechanical performance at the macro-scale. Fibre-filled CAN composites provided improved stiffness, but these effects were attributable primarily to the reinforcement rather than the dynamic network.

The overprinting experiments further indicated that CAN-based materials did not achieve the anticipated enhancement in interfacial bonding. Although higher printing temperatures improved rib strength, the absolute peel strengths remained in the range of the standard deviation, thus no significant improvement could be recorded, not even with annealing. The dynamic covalent chemistry, while theoretically advantageous, did not yield a practical bonding benefit under the tested conditions and equipment with this material combination.

Overall, the investigations carried out within Task 1.4 show that, although the CAN formulations were successfully prepared in the required forms for AM and hybrid processing, their implementation did not yet yield improvements in bonding performance when overprinted onto IM substrates. While measurable changes in network structure were confirmed, these did not consistently translate into higher interfacial strength. The round-robin activities demonstrated that printer type and orientation remain dominant factors in determining dimensional accuracy, mechanical behaviour, and 3D printing quality. Nevertheless, the coordinated benchmarking across all beneficiaries and the associated partner provides valuable insight into the material and process limitations currently encountered. These outcomes establish a solid basis for defining best-practice strategies for enhancing hybrid bonding performance in future work and for guiding subsequent optimization of processing conditions and overprinting protocols.

Deviations from the GA

The presented report covers all the aspects of Task 1.4, without deviations from GA.

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